

LINGUISTIC MEANING OF SPEECH ABILITIES OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the linguistic meaning of the speaking skills of high school students. The development of linguistic competence and intercultural communication in various conditions is important for students to achieve their communication goals. It currently focuses on intercultural communication and provides linguistics and cultural studies. This is a new paradigm, culture is the goal, and language is the tool.*

Keywords: *high school students, foreign language, speech abilities, communication model, culture, competence.*

The popularity of a foreign language as a subject of study has increased significantly in recent decades. At the current stage of methodology development, a number of well-defined trends in foreign language teaching can be identified. Innovative phenomena reflected in the organization of teaching and the behavior strategy of the teacher lead to the abandonment of the previously dominant paradigm of “knowledge” and the transition to personality, from the “communication model” to interactive methods. As stated by A.N.Shchukin, the focus of today’s methodists is joint effective play, organization of learning in cognitive activity, that is, activity directed at a collective subject [1]. This direction is based on the main features of language emphasized by communicative linguistics. They are as follows:

- communication (language is a means of communication),
- systematicity (linguistic tools are mutually organized),
- functionality (linguistic tools).
- communication, express (for content).

The following rules of communicative linguistics are relevant in the modern educational concept. The speaker becomes a criterion for choosing a speech act, and a speech model becomes a way of realizing the content of a speech act. The ultimate goal of the training is to develop verbal thinking. Communicative competence – is the ability to solve communication problems that are relevant for students in everyday, educational, industrial and cultural life using a foreign language.

“The ability to use language and speech facts or the ability to implement linguistic competence in different conditions of speech communication” is important for realization of communication goals of the student [2]. In addition, today the main direction of methodological research is aimed at intercultural communication, which is provided with linguistics and cultural studies. The program includes aspects such as non-equivalent vocabulary, basic knowledge, non-verbal communication tools and teaching phraseology. Recently, a new paradigm has appeared in the methodology: culture is the goal, language is the tool.

Teaching tools such as personal computers have become widespread in foreign language teaching. Optimizing teaching through various types of technical educational tools satisfies the methodological principle of complexity, but the impact of technologies is felt only when they are used purposefully and systematically, without breaking the general logic of the lesson. Nowadays, a person should be formed not only as a specialist in a field, but also as a person who knows foreign

languages and information technologies well, has a broad outlook and knowledge. In this regard, the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-5117 “On measures to bring the activity of popularizing the study of foreign languages to the next level in terms of quality” creates and develops the scope of language proficiency levels. The problem of determining the requirements for the purpose and content of teaching, corresponding to a certain level, as well as test control problems, is considered as a proof of intensive consideration.

It is important to take into account their psychological and age characteristics in order to analyze the effective methods of developing speech thinking and communication skills in a foreign language among high school students. Zimnyaya characterized each of the three young groups of high school students as an active, purposeful, internally motivated “subject of educational activity” with their socio-psychological and individual characteristics [3]. Artur Vladimirovich Petrovsky put forward the idea that: “...each age is characterized by many changes, which together form its own image of the personality structure” [4], in addition, students’ developmental changes according to teaching conditions (L.A. Wenger; P.Ya. Galperin, D.B. Elkonin, V.V. Davydov, D.I. Feldshtein) were dealt with by the above scientists. B.G. Ananyev defines high school students as 15-17 years old; A.N. Shchukin - 16-18 years old; VV Davydov - 15-17-18 years old (Ananyev B.G, 1981; Shchukin A.N, 2012, Davyidov V.V, 1986). Practice shows that the average age of high school students is 15-18 years old. *Elkonin Danil Borisovich* characterized high school age as a period of education and professional activity [5] and emphasized the importance of “I” ability. High school seniors go through a period of early teenage problems and conflicts. At this age, the desire to improve communication, more differentiation and self-regulation in the expression of emotional states increases. During this period, mutual understanding in communication becomes an important factor of self-esteem. For a teenager, this serves as evidence of his social and human value (I.Yu. Kulagina, 1998).

At the same time, high school students strive for behavioral, emotional, moral and value independence, and student’s personality emerges [6] Self-awareness in the professional field is carried out when choosing an educational institution and field of study [7]. Due to education and professional activity, high school students aged 15 to 17-18 develop “need for work, professional interests” [8].

The thinking of senior schoolchildren has a personal, emotional character. Here, intellectual activity acquires a special “thinking” associated with the desire of high school students to develop their own worldview and self-awareness. It is this “thinking” (not intellectual operations) that creates the uniqueness of the thinking of students of secondary school age. High school students not only build a general picture of the world, but also develop their own attitude to everything they know and see. Therefore, his mental activity combines the activity of thought analysis, intellectual inclination, emotionality and impressionability.

In foreign language classes, it is important for students of 10-11th grade to think actively, pay attention to solving mental problems, logical arrangement and systematization, search for universal patterns of thinking, independently find ways of direction generalized in the material. At this age, it is important for the student to understand the essence and meaning of actions and the general scheme of specific actions and activities, interested in synthesizing parts and wholes, particular and general, and not acquiring individual facts, details. Limiting the foreign language learning activities of upper secondary school students to mechanical repetition and memorization will respond to his active internal resistance and will ultimately be less effective. A.N.Shchukin

said that high school students are not focused on the amount of knowledge, but on its practical application. [1]

Today, the educational standards of general English education ensure that students acquire the following communication skills: reading, listening, writing and speaking. Language is the main means of communication, therefore, when teaching a foreign language, the teacher should pay special attention to the types of speech activities. However, the teacher faces various challenges and students' acquisition of communicative competence depends on overcoming them. It should be noted that communicative actions provide social competence, the ability to engage in communication, the ability to build constructive interactions with the interlocutor, and others.

The problem of developing speech skills in teaching a foreign language is a topical issue, because in modern conditions, not enough time is allocated to the development of students' speech skills in the educational process, which causes a number of problems, as a result of which students have to pronounce sentences with their subsequent pronunciation, cannot compose competently, have no understanding spoken English, and have difficulties in writing and reading. In addition, students may encounter linguistic noise, extra linguistic difficulties, language barriers, and other aspects that hinder the development of students' speaking skills.

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